

Covid -19 Pandemic and Inter- State Migrant Workers – An Analysis in the Context of Existing Laws

*A Dissertation Submitted to the University of Burdwan for the Partial fulfilment of
the requirement for the Degree of Master of Law*

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Certificate of Supervisor

I have great pleasure in certifying that Sumanta Narayan Podder, student of LL.M. 4th Semester, having Roll –BUR LLM (SEM) 2019/40, Reg. No. A-72 of 2016-17, Session - 2019-2021 of University of Burdwan, has written his Dissertation on **“COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND INTER-STATE MIGRANT WORKERS – AN ANALYSIS IN THE CONTEXT OF EXISTING LAWS”** under my supervision as partial fulfilment of LL.M. 4th Semester.

This is to certify that the candidate has done the work himself and I wish him all success in his life.

.....
Debabrata Basu
(Supervisor)

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the Dissertation entitled “*COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND INTER-STATE MIGRANT WORKERS – AN ANALYSIS IN THE CONTEXT OF EXISTING LAWS*” submitted to the University of Burdwan, in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of **Master of Law** is a record of original research work done by me under the supervision and guidance of Mr. Debabrata Basu, Assistant Professor of Law, Hooghly Mohsin College. This work has not previously formed the complete Thesis or Dissertation or any other work for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Fellowship or other similar Title or Recognition.

Sumanta Narayan Podder

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Dated:

PREFACE

The present study of critical analysis regarding the state of life and living off the inter-state migrant workers of this country during the raging pandemic due to SARS-CoV-2 or Novel Coronavirus, causing a widespread infectious disease named COVID-19 and deaths worldwide.

This critical study specifically analyses the plight of the interstate migrant workers and the government response to that and the state of legal provisions regarding the rights of the migrant workers. Historically migrant workers exist from an ancient period in this country and they are essential for the good health of our economy. The Indian kind of economy was largely informal before the introduction of the liberalisation of the Indian market in the early nineties under the instructions of world neoliberal policy headed by IMF. After the market reforms, it was seen that the character of the Indian state underwent a paradigm shift slowly from a constitutionally mandated welfare state to a populist state, and the speed of that transformation has increased post-2014 elections.

Hence, the current study and analysis have an immense social, political, economic, and legal relevance in the present day. The Central Government has already officially stated in the parliament that they do not possess any data regarding the plight of the migrant workers in the lockdown period induced by the raging coronavirus pandemic. Hence, the existing laws and the entire legal framework has failed to address the situation and needs of the migrant workers. The migrant workers, who constitute more than 90% of India's workforce and have helped to build India's US\$2.9 trillion economies suffer the most and face the weakness social protection systems.

The focus of this study is aimed at the analysis of the experiences of Covid-19 induced lockdown by the inter-state migrant workers. The chief function of laws and statutes and Ordinances and Rules or Government Orders and Notices are to create a balance of convenience where the focus lies in the maximum convenient situation of a large section of people. But the present Coronavirus-induced lockdown has failed the proposition. Numerous instructions and S.O.P.s have been published by the Government of India from time to time that has had the opposite effect. Those have made more critical the plight of numerous migrant workers working in various informal sectors.

The entire legal regime relating to labour and unorganised sector and migrant workers has failed them during the period of lockdown due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CrPC	Criminal Procedure Code
ECOSOC	Economic and Social Council
EDA	Epidemic Diseases Act
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
HPC	High Power Committee
IPC	Indian Penal Code
IPEC	International Programme on the Elimination of Child Labour
ICCPR	International Convention on Civil and Political Rights
ICESCR	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
ILO	International Labour Organisation
LPA	Letters Patent Appeal
PIL	Public Interest Litigation
NCEUS	National Commission for Enterprise in the Unorganised Sector
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
SC	Supreme Court
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UN	United Nations
WP	Writ Petition
WHO	World Health Organisation

LIST OF STATUTES IN CHRONOLOGICAL ORDER

1. *Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897*
2. *Payment of Wages Act, 1936*
3. *Employment of Children Act, 1938*
4. *Employers' Liability Act, 1938*
5. *Weekly Holiday Act, 1942*
6. *Industrial Employment (Standing Orders) Act, 1946*
7. *Industrial Disputes Act, 1947*
8. *Employees State Insurance Act, 1948*
9. *Factories Act, 1948*
10. *Minimum Wages Act, 1948*
11. *Plantation Labour Act, 1951*
12. *Employees' Provident Funds & Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952*
13. *Maternity Benefit Act, 1961*
14. *Personal Injuries (Compensation Insurance) Act, 1963*
15. *Payment of Bonus Act, 1965*
16. *Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act, 1970*
17. *Inter State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Condition of Service) Act, 1979*
18. *Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993*
19. *Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996*
20. *Building and Other Construction Workers' Welfare Cess Act, 1996*
21. *Disaster Management Act, 2005*
22. *Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005*
23. *Unorganized Workers' Social Security Act, 2008*
24. *Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009*
25. *National Food Security Act, 2013*
26. *Street Vending Act, 2014*
27. *Code on Wages, 2019*
28. *Industrial Relations Code, 2020*

29. *Occupational Safety, Health and Working Conditions Code, 2020*
30. *Code on Social Security, 2020*

Introduction

*“Hum Burma ki galiyon me
Aur tum ho Dehradun
Tumhari yaad satati hai
...
Mere piya gaye Rangoon
Kiya hai wahan se telephone
Tumhari yaad satati hai”¹*

These are excerpts from a popular song used in the 1949 Indian film *Patanga*, directed by *Harnam Singh Rawali*. He was born in Lyallpur, Pakistan, British India and later moved to Mumbai for a film career. The song in the melancholy and famous voice of *Shamshad Begum* in this classic Hindi film about a wife bemoaning her migrant husband’s absence in the backdrop of World War II in the middle of the 20th century is an echo of the feelings of millions of women before. Rangoon in Burma, now Yangon and Myanmar respectively, happened to be one of the important places in the world that were the destination for millions of Indian migrant workers in the early 20th century, but similar voices can be unearthed across the world in songs, letters, and books across eras. India is different. The journey of Indian migrant workers is different. The separated families of the Indian migrant workers had to wait for the postman to arrive to deliver letters and then for fleeting re-unions. The pain and anguish involved in this double layer wait were perennial and almost never-ending. Now cut to modern-day Bollywood.

*Ye log jo footpath pe sote hain - Kaun haain ye log? Kahan
se aate hain ye? Unke pas na rehne ko ghar hai, na rozgar
hain, na paisa hain; phir kyun chale aate hain humare
khusoorat shahron ko unki khoobsoorti pe batta lagane?²*

This is a part of a passionate speech delivered by the character named *Advocate Jagdish Tyagi* aka *Jolly* in a PIL Case in his concluding argument in a 2013 Indian film

¹ <http://www.lyricsgram.com/song/mere-piya-gaye-rangun-25234>

² https://www.scripts.com/script/jolly_llb_11382

Jolly LLB, directed by Subhash Kapoor. In this film, the character of the protagonist and a struggling lawyer Jolly is also a migrant. He migrated from his hometown Meerut to Delhi to ensure a better living and to become a “*star lawyer*”. Who is not a migrant?

If we come to Bengal, there are lots of popular culture we find associated with the lives of migrant workers.

Chol Mini Assam jabo, deshe baro dukh re
*Assam deshe re cha bagan voriya*³

...

Babu bhayar chhana pona
Ishkul pore jay re
Hamar chhana poka bichhe khay
*Ehe sokhi jiyeye upaay*⁴

...

Rail gari kaisan sundar
Cholo deikhye jabo
Vitoreto aaigo paani
Oporeto loha loti
*Haora soman chole lage nathar shyam*⁵

All these are masterpieces from Bengali and Assamese folk songs that describe the plight and hardship faced by the migrant workers from Bengal to Assam and other places on and from the sixties and seventies. Hence, it's an undeniable fact that the problem of migrant workers is well entwined in the lifeblood of this country, be it West Bengal, Maharashtra, or Punjab, Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, Gujarat, or other states of India. Even large migrations have occurred towards India from Bangladesh and Nepal, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Afghanistan from time immemorial and in present times. The history of India cannot be written without proper writing and documenting the history of migrants. Although we are here concerned specifically with the migrant workers who are statutorily defined as such, but large human migrations

³ <http://kalidasgupta.com/kaliced.2.html>

⁴ <http://kalidasgupta.com/kaliced.2.html>

⁵ <http://kalidasgupta.com/kaliced.2.html>

have been occurring from ancient times. It is an innate human nature to search for better living and better earnings. That's why they constantly migrate in search of those and create new settlements and habitats. This is the history of the entire world. The history of human civilization is also the history of migration. Also, some environmental migrants are in different positions to those that migrate in search of food and shelter and earning. These are people who are made migrants by the corporate plunder of nature – forests, rivers, mining, building housings, etc. Never has the chronicle of these migrants documented in history. But the current study has a very limited scope, and hence it is to limit its discussions within the chosen area. Now let us discuss some crude data.

The Economic Survey of 2018-19⁶ reflects that almost 93% of the total workforce of India is informal. Also, the Report on the Committee on Unorganized Sector Statistics⁷ of the NSC 2012 states that the informal workforce in India is more than 90% of the total workforce. Unorganised workers in India have increased manifolds post-independence.⁸ Around 50% of the GDP of India is contributed by the unorganised sector according to National Commission for Enterprise in the Unorganised Sector (NCEUS).

The chief problem faced by the migrant workers is the gross violation of their innate and inalienable human rights that they possess being human by their employers as well as the Government. These rights can never be taken away or waived under any circumstances. But we have seen that the definition of Human Rights as defined in Section 2(d) of the *Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993* as '*Human Rights means the rights relating to life, liberty, equality and dignity of the individual guaranteed by the Constitution or embodied in the International Covenants and enforceable by the courts in India*' does not have any meaning in respect of the migrant workers, especially during the nationwide lockdown. This is the area that the model of the welfare state as constitutionally mandated falls short and in times it is shattered.

⁶ *The Economic Survey* of 2018-19 released on 4th July 2019

⁷ Report of National Statistic Commission (NSC) 2012

⁸ Nitika Diwakar and Taqffiqu Ahmed, "*Problems and Challenges faced by unorganised sector: An Indian perspective*", *New Man International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, Vol. 1, Issue 12, 2014, pp. 32.

Objectives of Current Research

The migrant workers of various hues and colours fall under the broad category of unorganised workers. Although certain provisions have been made for them in a bunch of statutes, they are mostly not entitled to get the benefits of the statutory provisions. The reasons behind this situation are manifold, but the most common reason is the apathy of their employers as well as the apathy of the State and Central Government to bargain with the employers who employ the migrant workers mostly under inhuman conditions and the employment contracts are illegal. Hence, the targeted objectives of the present study are:

- To analyze and evaluate the beneficial and protective statutory provisions;
- To examine and evaluate the beneficial schemes provided under different Acts and Rules;
- To critically analyze and evaluate the necessary enforcement of the Beneficial Schemes;
- To analyze and evaluate the drawbacks and/or limitations in the main Act.

Justification for the Current Study

According to the considered opinion of the researcher, the migrant workers are the most vulnerable among all the working population. They do not have a fixed income or fixed workplace. Some are seasonal migrants, and hence they move a thousand kilometres every season to find jobs that are meagre-paying and uncertain. Since the rural economy of India is chiefly dependant on harvesting and agriculture and the present era market system has made the farmer its most exploited target, the rural population has been gradually shifting towards various odd jobs in the cities and towns and above all the megacities. They are leaving their land and village and becoming migrant labourers just to earn a better living for their family which is otherwise difficult if they depend only on agricultural produce. There are a host of statutes and rules and Acts to provide them social security and protect them. But these are seldom of any use since the migrant workers are either unconscious about it, or they are so much exploited that they do not have any other way out but to live with that exploitation. They are termed as unorganised workers since they are not unionised and they do not have a fixed wage and other remunerations according to the provisions of various labour laws.

These are the reasons why they are most at danger due to a nationwide sudden lockdown in 2020 and gradual targeted lockdowns in 2021. Hence the topic mentioned and above-named is well justified to be glanced into further and have research done to point out the problems and anomalies.

Formation of the Research Problem

Identifying a research problem is indicating a specific area for answering some research questions. Depending upon the nature of the research undertaken, the research problem is formulated, i.e., research may be explanatory, exploratory, or theoretical.

Zikmund (1988:67) has said that the selection of the problem is to be linked with the following: What is the purpose of the study? How much is already known? Is additional information necessary? What is to be ascertained or measured? How is it to be measured? Can the required data be collected? Is the present time appropriate for undertaking the research? Can a hypothesis be formulated?

Although the problem regarding the chosen topic is as clear as daylight in that the plight and hardships faced by the migrant workers are huge, let us discuss briefly in a formal manner the identification of the problem on the chosen topic.

The entire management of the current Covid-19 Pandemic in India relies upon an archaic Act from the British colonial period. The Act, named *Epidemic Disease Act, 1897* was enacted by the Britishers to tackle the outbreak of bubonic Plague in Bombay. But the fact is, the Act does not tell anything about actual disease mitigation. It only empowers the state as well as the central government with special powers which they can use upon ordinary and common Indians who would not obey the authorities, etc. By no means it contains any provisions regarding welfare measure to be taken by the State to mitigate the hardships of the huge toiling mass crippled under the colonial rule of the Britishers. And by no means it contains any provisions relating to the migrant workers since the issues related to them were not codified at that time. Hence, enacting such archaic laws in the twenty-first century to combat a pandemic of this large scale certainly calls for criticism of the Government after so many years of our independence from the Britishers. Hence, the principal Act which is being used to combat the present pandemic and imposed lockdown is not of any help for the millions of migrant workers.

Instead, they are being manhandled and beaten by the administration using this archaic and irrelevant Act that increase their sufferings much more.

In addition to the above Act, the Indian Act being used and enacted to combat the Covid-19 pandemic is *The Disaster Management Act, 2005*. This Act was framed by the Government of India to combat natural and environmental calamities, whether they are induced by human activities and/or naturally occurring. From the definition of disaster⁹ from Sec 2(d) of the said Act, this becomes clear. The Act chiefly focuses not on the management of any disease and/or pandemic, but on the formation of a National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA), with the Prime Minister as its chairperson. This forms a hierarchy of administrative officers and excludes any participation of elected local representatives, local communities, civic groups and NGOs. Thus, it fosters a beurocratic, command and control type top-down authority that gives the Central, State and District authorities sweeping powers. The various Sections, specifically 51, 52, 54 and others of this Act betray the fact that the administration, as well as the bureaucracy, have almost unlimited and sweeping powers to convict anyone based upon some abstract concepts that have nothing to do with concerning any pandemic or disease. This is not also any welfare legislation, hence, too much reliance upon this Act in combating the present pandemic, in conjunction with the *Epidemic Disease Act 1897*, has made the life of the tolling people of this country more miserable.

Now let us come to various labour legislations that are made for labour welfare. But unfortunately, these legislations help a little in mitigating the plight of the migrant workers as they are all unorganised workers and hence their problems are not at all addressed in these labour legislations. These are very important labour welfare legislations that have been enacted by the legislature keeping in mind the hardships faced by the industrial as well as other labourers and its Constitutional mandate to minimise it. But these Acts have not come into effect only upon the sweet will of the legislators. There is a long history of struggles by the workers of all over the world from the start of the Scientific and Technological Revolution in Britain and the Western

⁹ Sec 2(d): “disaster” means a catastrophe, mishap, calamity or grave occurrence in any area, arising from natural or man-made causes, or by accident or negligence which results in substantial loss of life or human suffering or damage to, and destruction of, property, or damage to, or degradation of, environment, and is of such a nature or magnitude as to be beyond the coping capacity of the community of the affected area;

World. The historic *Hay Market Affair* in 1886¹⁰ marks the beginning of industrial workers' struggle against all the oppression being faced by them due to the increasing demands of the capitalist mode of production to maximise the profits of the industrialists and capitalists. Even in this era, the struggle continues, though in a different form.

Then there are specific legislations enacted for the benefit of the migrant labourers of several kinds. But we shall see that even these Acts could not save this class of workers from facing a disaster relating to their life and living during the Nationwide lockdown due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Hence the problem is well justified from the title – are the laws cumulatively enough to mitigate the plight of the migrant workers during this raging pandemic and a Nationwide lockdown due to that?

Very little study has been done in respect of the children of the migrant workers who have been left out of school due to their parents' plight of losing a job and returning home. Although the *Right to Education Act, 2009* is comprehensive legislation to ensure free and compulsory education of children up to 14 years of age, even this legislation could not keep the promise of compulsory and free education of the children it made during the Nation-wide lockdown. Hence, the problem of the present study can be viewed from this point of view also.

From the above discussion, the problem presented by the present study is unambiguous. Since this is a critical study, the researcher will critically comment upon the Acts and the measures taken by the State as well as the Central Governments in keeping the life and living of the migrant workers in a good and humane shape during the Nation-wide lockdown due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Literature Survey

For any research work or study, review of existing literature is extremely important so as not to repeat any previous study and avoid plagiarism. Literature forms the basis of any new or further study on the relevant topic. The literature comprises various academic works like books, publications, reports, notifications, commentary, etc. which must be studied before any research work or critical study is taken at hand. The extent of homework done on the research topic and literature consultation is

¹⁰ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Haymarket-Affair>

directly related to the quality of the final report produced by the researcher. The main aspect of a literature review is that it judges, sums up, compares, and contrasts and connects various books, articles, other relevant sources that are very much related to the present study. A good literature review ensures that a proper research question has been asked, and a proper theoretical framework or research methodology have been chosen.

There are four types of literature review: a) evaluative, b) exploratory, c) instrumental and d) systematic (or meta-analysis). In the present research, the researcher has used exploratory and systematic type of literature review.

Research Design

The research design or research is taken before the actual beginning of the research activity. Any research is valid only when its conclusions are true. It is reliable when the findings are reproducible. Reliability and validity of the research require the planning of inquiry, i.e., the detailed strategy of how the research will be conducted. A good research design depends on two aspects – a) specifying the thing that the researcher wants to find out properly phrasing the problem and the issues to be studied or the logical structuring of the inquiry to be made, and b) determining the *modus operandi* of it, i.e., how to do it. The second aspect includes collecting data through scientific and appropriate methods using different techniques of data analysis and rational and meaningful deduction(s).

According to **Henry Manheim** (177:140), research design not only anticipates and specifies the seemingly countless decisions connected with carrying out data collection, processing, and analysis, but it presents a logical basis for these decisions.

William Zikmund (1988:41) has described research design as a “*master plan specifying the methods and procedures for collecting and analysing the needed information*”.

Martin Bulmer (1974:84) has said that “*research design is the specification of the problem, conceptual definitions, derivation of hypotheses to test, and defining of the population to be studied*”.

Ackoff Russell (1961:52) maintains that research design is “*planning various phases and procedures relating to the formulation of research efforts*”.

Let us now have a brief outlook towards various phases in research design in a tabular form¹¹:

Research Methodology

In common parlance, research means a search for knowledge. Also, research can be defined as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. In short, research is the art of scientific investigation. **D. Slesinger** and **M. Stephenson** define research in *The Encyclopaedia of Social Sciences* as, “the manipulation of things, concepts or symbols to generalise to extend, correct or verify knowledge, whether that knowledge aids in the construction of theory or the practice of an art.” Research is thus an original contribution towards the existing knowledge stock and thus making for advancement. It is the pursuit of truth with help of study, observation, comparison, and experiment.

Now let us conceptualise ourselves with the difference between research methods and research methodology. Research methods may be understood as all those methods or techniques that are used for the conduction of research. Thus, the research methods refer to the methods the researchers employ to perform research operations. Whereas research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In this, we study various steps that are generally adopted by the researchers in studying his research problem along with the logic behind them. Research methodology has various dimensions and research methods do constitute a part of the research

¹¹ Ahuja, Ram “*Research Methods*” Rawat Publications 2020

methodology. The scope of research methodology is much wider than that of research methods.

The current research methodology adopted by the researcher is analytical and the researcher uses a doctrinal method to acquire facts for his study. In the analytical method, the researcher uses facts and/or information already available at hand and analyses them to make a critical evaluation. For this to do, the doctrinal method can be used where reference would be made of two types of sources: a) Statutes, Acts, Rules, etc as Primary Sources, and b) Books, Journals, Websites etc as secondary sources. The most authentic source describing the topic properly would have been the direct accounts from the migrant workers themselves, but it was not always possible in this period of pandemic and hence they are taken from published resources where necessary.

Research Questions

After the research objectives have been ascertained and set up, the research questions must be constituted. Research questions constitute the most important element of any kind of research. These are not research objectives. They describe the ideas contained in the research objectives. They tend to point out the data that are required to be collected in a study.

Neuman (1997:122) and **Blaikie** (2000:65-67) have offered some techniques of developing research questions, like – record all questions that occur in mind after going through the literature or discussions with others, review all these questions and determine whether all of them are necessary or not and delete those which are outside the scope of current research, classify questions based on their nature and finally examine the scope of the questions that are finally chosen.

Based on the above, the researcher has chosen and formulated the following research questions for the present critical study on the condition of the migrant workers in the age of Covid-19 pandemic and the nationwide lockdown due to that.

- What are the laws that have been enacted by the legislature for the migrant workers?
- Whether these laws are sufficient for the benefit and welfare of the target group?

- Whether the existing laws have been properly implemented and enforced by the competent authority?
- Whether the migrant workers are receiving social security benefits from the Government?

Hypothesis

According to **Theodorson and Theodorson** (1969:191), “*a hypothesis is a tentative statement asserting a relationship between certain facts.*”

Kerlinger (1973:8) describes it as “*a conjectural statement of the relationship between two or more variables*”

Black and Champion (1976:126) have described it as “*a tentative statement about something, the validity of which is usually unknown*”

Webster (1968) has defined hypothesis as “*a tentative assumption made to draw out and test its logical or empirical consequences*”

Thus, a hypothesis is an assumption about the relations between variables. It is a tentative explanation of the research problem or a guess about the the research outcome.

Keeping in mind all the above, the researcher has formulated the following hypothesis for his critical study as:

“The existing legal structure of both legal provisions and their implementation to safeguard the interests of migrant workers in an emergency situation like a Nation-wide pandemic are not sufficient”

CHAPTER – 1

History of Pandemics

“Our Dead are never dead to us until we have forgotten them”

- Mary Evans/ George Elliot¹²

We live in the 21st century and living in this era doesn't feel like living in a time two hundred years ago. At that time people barely lived before they died. They would celebrate an average of twenty-five birthdays in their entire lifetime. Mass mortality due to war, famine, natural disasters, and epidemics was a way of life then. When mankind fought few wars, understood how to prevent famines, grew resilient to natural disasters, and learned how to control the spread of a disease, only then they started living longer. And last but not the least, when medical science developed to the state what it is now. But before going into a short account of the history of pandemics and epidemics, let us have an outlook over the timeline of the pandemics that occurred historically.

1817

The onset of Cholera Pandemic

1866

Third International Sanitary Conference held in Constantinople (Istanbul)

(First two conferences were held in Paris in 1851 and 1859)

1894

Third Plague Pandemic

(Onset of first two being in the 6th Century CE and 14th Century CE)

1918

Influenza Pandemic

(Milder prior outbreak in 1889)

¹² George Eliot, *Adam Bede* (John B. Alden, 1884 edition; first published in 1859), p. 95. George Eliot was the pen name of Mary Ann Evans (1819–1880).

Death Toll Estimates in Millions

Pandemics	Period	World	India
Cholera	1817-1920	19	8
Plague	1894-1920	13	12
Influenza	1918-1920	40	20
Total	1817-1920	72	40

Various parts of the world started their journeys out of mass mortality at different times. In India, this journey began in 1920¹³. Between 1920 and 2020, death rates in India fell considerably from 45/1000 people to 7/1000 people. At present, an average Indian can expect to celebrate at least seventy-five birthdays.¹⁴ This is a remarkable advancement.

Between 1817 and 1920, approximately over twenty million people died all over the world because of several pandemics. This is a figure much greater than the number killed by wars. Principally three diseases – cholera, plague and influenza caused this, and it is a historical fact that India was at the epicentre of this.

Epidemic, Endemic and Pandemic

For disease outbreaks, we frequently encounter these three terms. Now are these three the same? No. If these three were the same, we would not have three separate terms for them. Also, there are terms like *epizootic* and *panzootic*. But these are out of the context of our present study. But a common factor of all the diseases to become epidemic or pandemic is to be communicable and contagious. The more the disease being communicable, the more it has chances to become a pandemic.

For a disease to become epidemic, it must suddenly affect many members of the same community simultaneously. Here time, i.e., simultaneity is more important than national boundaries. The simultaneity is connected to the seasonality of the disease. It happens at times that we frequently visit doctor's clinic when seasons change. When

¹³ Guha, Sumit, “*Health and Population in South Asia: From Earliest Times to the Present*” (Permanent Black, 2001)

¹⁴ Dyson, Tim, “*A Population History of India: From the First Modern People to the Present Day*” (Oxford University Press, 2018), pp. 256 and 280.

that happens periodically and is localized, those diseases are *endemic* in respect of that region only. An *endemic* may or may not turn *epidemic* each time depending on the rate of transmission.

For an *epidemic* to develop as a *pandemic*, both *time* and *space* are equally imperative the disease must cross adequately wide national boundaries to become a *pandemic*. What is meant by the term ‘wide’ has characteristically been a judgemental call linking either countries or continents as the local parts. The use of the word ‘*pandemic*’ is new; in the last century only. Outbursts of several diseases in the nineteenth century were loosely termed *epidemics*, but now they are classified as *pandemics*. Hence, the main point is simultaneous transmission across countries and not the severity. World Health Organization (WHO) designates diseases as *pandemics* considering their severity¹⁵.

A huge controversy occurred when in 2009 WHO dropped *severity* from the definition of *pandemics*. In 2009, H1N1 influenza was declared a *pandemic* by WHO, but eventually, it came out to be as mild as the seasonal flu¹⁶. The announcement of the *pandemic* was then questioned. There seemed to be existing links between WHO advisors and corporate pharma industries that benefited from vaccination¹⁷. Thus, it is apparent from this that designating a disease outbreak as a *pandemic* is somewhat a political decision as it involves international trade and business and relations between countries. But a careful reading of history shows that *pandemics* are intimately linked with disease severity.

The Outbreak of Covid-19

On 30 December 2019, a young doctor in Wuhan posted on social media news of a disease outbreak that resembled SARS (*Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome*)¹⁸. Eventually, this new disease was declared a *pandemic* on 11th March 2020 and named Covid-19 by the World Health Organisation.

From the experience of a long history of *pandemics*, it can be inferred that there can be no specific pattern of the time when *pandemics* would occur. The world, as it

¹⁵ ‘The Classical Definition of a Pandemic is not Elusive’, *Bulletin of the WHO*, 89 (2011): 540–41

¹⁶ Harrison, Mark, “*Pandemics*”

¹⁷ *ibid*

¹⁸ Green, Andrew, “*Obituary of Li Wenliang*”, *The Lancet*, Vol. 395, February 29, 2020: 682.

became more and more connected through globalization and revolutionary improvement of conveyance, it left the age of pandemics behind it, and it is a mystery why pandemics did not occur within the last hundred years as large an extent as they did before 1920. The bacteria, virus and several other microscopic organisms mutate continuously in natural environments and hence it is impossible to predict when and where they would cause a disease outbreak. Thus, *pandemics* can never be eradicated, only thing is that they can be contained.

Covid-19 Pandemic in India

The previous outbreaks of diseases in human history clearly show that closing transport systems suddenly is not so well-thought proposition. During the outbreaks and resulting closing down of the transport system, people working in places other than their homeland certainly want and try to go back to their homes desperately; their movement will furthermore augment and amplify the spreading of the disease. Thus, to stop the further progress of the disease, planning should be made properly to contain the disease in a smaller place.

If we consider the movements across the borders, the suspension of visas and other permits may be considered gradually, not abruptly. If an amount of time is provided to those stranded, they can make some arrangements for them and then the governments can step in to arrange for those still stranded. The sign of a welfare state is that the students and other vulnerable groups like migrant workers should be cleared first before any stringent lockdown measure is adopted and implemented as a policy to contain the spread of infection or disease. The scenario is totally different when we consider internal migrations or movements. Because like international movement stoppage, internal movement cannot be stopped suddenly. This is because many people are working in many places other than their native place and if suddenly every mode of transportation is stopped, they will simply choose to walk towards their homes.

If we look at the history of pandemics in this country, in 1896, during the outbreak of plague, the Bombay Government did not shut down all the means of conveyance at once, because it was argued that then the migrants will scatter around throughout a large area and then the control and identification would become much

more difficult¹⁹. History shows that people have a cultural and emotional inclination towards dying in their land and own village than in any place foreign and this surpassed the fear of contracting the disease during return or prosecution under any law. Exactly this happened in the history of China, when in 1911, people chose to walk to their native places due to the shutdown of railways from the cities neglecting the possibilities of dying due to exhaustion or disease – the same reason which the British expected the people to do in India in 1896, and did not shut down the railways. It is a fact that the railways may increase the chance of the disease spread, but the idea that the shutdown of the railway system would contain the infection is not understandable on the ground that people still would have various means of travel.

This is called *reverse migration*, i.e., when people in considerable numbers flow back to the place from where they started migrating. And if all means of transportation is summarily shut down at the beginning of a widespread pandemic, this will occur, and the respective government must be prepared to combat the resulting situation and the increased possibility of disease spread. In 2020 in China, before the Wuhan outbreak took place, hundreds of millions of people from the cities had gone to their native places due to the lunar festivals, and it is rendered as the world's largest migration. This is the reason why a stringent transport shutdown was not necessary from the beginning of the outbreak. If those migrant workers were stopped by stopping the transport system in response to the pandemic, the worst scenario was to be anticipated²⁰. At that time though, the Indian Government was not at all ready with even a preliminary response plan!

On 24th March 2020, the Prime Minister of India, in his speech on television, announced a complete lockdown for twenty-one days and a sudden stoppage of the entire railway system from midnight of that very date. Notably, there were no words spent on the migrant workers or on the people who were outside of their native places for work or any other reason, maybe for medical treatment purposes. This announcement was contradictory to the 2016-17 reports of the *Economic Survey* of this same government where it mentioned that many people in this country are circular internal migrants and there exist no portable social security measures for them to be

¹⁹ Nathan, R., “*The Plague in India, 1896, 1897*” (Shimla, 1898), p. 293.

²⁰ Hiufu, Won, Maggie, ‘*3 Billion Journeys: World's Biggest Human Migration in China*’, CNN Travel, 10 January 2020.

availed offshore²¹. It is a correct argument that the migrant workers working in various places should have been provided a bit more time to return to their homes before the complete shutdown was implemented²². It was clear with reports at hands then that if the migrant workers would be deprived of their jobs at the places of their work in cities, but they could get some social security at the native homes, then the chance of returning to their homes must have been provided to them.

For the next two months, the balcony class, who acted following the instructions of the Prime Minister by paying respect to the frontline workers in various odd ways from the comfort of their secured house, witnessed horrific visuals of migrant workers being dehumanised every day in all possible ways in all possible corners of our country. When the middle-class was engrossed in the return of *Ramayana* serial on the TV and reminiscing good old days, the migrant workers were dying on road in their desperate attempts to return to their homes by any means. According to government data, 21,000 camps had been set up to provide shelter to over 500,000 stranded migrant workers. But if we add to this the number of workers walking or hitchhiking, the data no government possesses, the resulting number would be an immense one. The promise of winning the battle against Corona by the Prime Minister on 24th March failed miserably as the new cases were rising very fast. Due to this, the lockdown was extended many times. This made the workers returned to their homes angry and they started protesting. They visualised the complete inland shut down of transportation as being a hypocritical move from the government as the stoppage of international flights took more time, and even after the stoppage of the international flights, special flights were arranged by the government under *Vande Bharat* scheme to bring back those people stranded abroad. The matter was made worse as there was no coordination between the state governments and the central government regarding this.

Finally, in May, the government started *Shramik Special* trains to transport the stranded migrant workers and it carried near about 5 million migrants, though some trains were “lost” and they did not reach their destinations. Many workers died inside the trains. There were no options of drinking water or food inside the trains in that

²¹ *The Economic Survey of India*, 2016–17, Chapter 12, and the 2017 “*Report of the Working Group on Migration*” by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Poverty Alleviation.

²² Tumbbe, Chinmay, “*In times of a lockdown, support migrant workers*”, Hindustan Times, 26 March 2020.

scorching heat of Indian summer. A lot of people returned by buses also. This reverse migration of the workers finally occurred at a time when the rate of infection was much high than the beginning and this proves the failure of the original plan of locking down the people at the very onset of the pandemic.

CHAPTER – 2

History of Indian Migrant Workers

Unorganized labour has a long history of its existence. With the advent of the Scientific and Technological Revolution and the respective upper hand of capitalist economic production came the inherent problem of over-production and the crisis within the economic system. This has been seen in a circular motion in the countries where the capitalist economic production was at its boon. India was out of this market economy due to its Constitutional mandates of the welfare state and *laissez-faire* economy before the 1990s. After the 1990s, when the economic liberalisation was welcomed and the Indian market was being opened gradually for the world by linking it with the world market, the effect and pressure of the world market and its ups and downs altogether started affecting Indian market and the Indian economy too. Thus, the system gradually shifted towards populist economic policies rather than the constitutionally mandated welfare economic duties by the state. Elected members of the Parliament and the State Assemblies limited their activities and duties as law-makers by placing the mass who voted for and/or against them at the mercy of their political whims and fancies, making them believe that even the smallest performance of the MPs and MLAs in favour of public interest in any way is something that is enough for the public and no questions can be asked against that or in favour of any constitutionally-guaranteed rights and duties. This has become the very essence of parliamentary democracy nowadays and has put India's huge informal economy at the mercy of big and crony capitalists through privatisation of profitable public sectors. Those capitalists create the market rules with the inputs from giant corporate conglomerates. It has made the Indian market directly linked with the world market and has made human labour cheaper and jobs uncertain and underpaid.

The Indian labour market principally stands upon the labours of the unorganised workers because the market is still informal. With the rise of capitalistic economic system and the resulting extreme labour-exploitation, the farmers have also become agricultural workers, and in some places, bonded labourers of capitalism, and hence the job of farming does not yield much subsistence to the rural mass. Hence, they, in search of a bit more earning, come to the cities *en masse* to join the huge number of informal,

unorganised, and migrant labour force. This mass of labourers is a heterogeneous admixture and accounts for billions of household incomes. Hence, the issue of migrant workers and their contribution to the Indian economy can't be overlooked. Let us now have a brief account of the history of the migrant workers of India.

Royal Commission on Labour^{23,24,25} was constituted in 1929 by the British Government to enquire into and to report on the existing conditions of labour in industry. In 1944, the Government appointed another Labour Investigation Committee²⁶ to investigate the risk associated with their work in the industry. However, the Labour Investigation Committee was also constituted only for organized labour. After Independence, the Government of India in 1966 constituted the National Commission on Labour²⁷ to investigate the matter of the unorganised sector. But unfortunately, nothing was recommended by this Commission for the welfare of unorganized workers. However, the *Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979* regulates the employment of inter-State migrant workmen and provides for their conditions of service and matters connected therewith.

We do not have a place to discuss the detailed history of migration in India from time immemorial. The only fact to be mentioned here and discussed to a certain extent that the Indian case of migration is unique in its sheer persistence and magnitude of this phenomenon, one that has lasted for well over a century now. It is also a phenomenon that affects regions covering at least 20 per cent of the Indian population, currently comprising over 200 million people. This migration ranks among the largest and longest migration streams for work in the documented history of this country. It has led to the rise of cities like Mumbai and Kolkata. It has also produced several freedom fighters and political leaders who went on to become Presidents and *Bharat Ratna* awardees.

India's history of migration has always been dominated by males and it is almost a semi-permanent settlement. It yields remittance also. For a particular region, if more

²³ This Commission is popularly known as *Whitley Commission* constituted in 1929

²⁴ GOI, (1927), Report on the Royal Commission on Agriculture, Vol.II, Part I. Central Publication Branch, Government of India, Calcutta;

²⁵ GOI, (1931), Report of the Royal Commission on Labour in India, Central publication branch, Calcutta;

²⁶ The Labour Investigation Committee was appointed by the Government of India on 12 February 1944;

²⁷ This Commission was constituted by the resolution of Ministry of Labour, Employment and Rehabilitation, vide no. 36/14/66-1&e dated 24th December 1966, New Delhi. This Commission submitted its report to Government in 1969. This Commission is also known as the first National Commission on Labour;

than 20% of people are out of their homes for earning a living in other places, it can be said that the source-region contains mass-migration. This mass migration for work elsewhere is said to be male-dominated when about 70% of the male population from that source region go away for work. By semi-permanent settlement, it is meant that those going out for earning a living do not return often, and also they do not permanently settle in their workplace either. They may return after decades or after some year and go back. Remittances are the amount of money that the migrant going for work send to their families at home for living and subsistence.

In India, the history of migration has its own ups and downs, and it is directly linked with the world economic system, as like other countries' migrations. We can safely divide the timeline of Indian migration in phases depending upon varied economic atmosphere of the country, like that occurred from 19th century to 1930, then up to 1991, and then post-liberalisation era after 1991. Migration for work has always yielded labour-intensive works, as was the scenario beginning from 1830s, from when India's organised migration started. At earlier times, the labour was bonded, it was contractual for generally 5-10 years of times, and within that tie, the labourer was not free to change the contractor. After the period of contract was over, s/he was free to change the contractor and move to other contractors. It was the era of the Colonial Plantation economy, and the type of labour was, in essence, slavery.

Starting from the 1830s up to the 1920s, about 2 million people were transported towards the Caribbean, Mauritius, South Africa and Fiji, Hawaii, Peru, Cuba etc. almost 70% of these transportations were from India and 20% from China. All these labourers were bonded or indentured²⁸. *“Within India, Calcutta was the leading port of embarkation followed by Madras and, very rarely, Bombay. By the late 19th century, of those who left from Calcutta, two-thirds were recruited from present-day east Uttar Pradesh, a fifth from central India, a tenth from Punjab and very few from Bihar even though it was an important site initially”*²⁹.

Around India, the bonded labour or the indentured labour system started through migrations to Burma and Malaya³⁰. That was Colonial era and the British exploitative

²⁸ Northrup, David, *“Indentured Labour in the Age of Imperialism, 1834–1922”* (Cambridge University Press, 1995), Table A.1.

²⁹ Tinker, *“A New System of Slavery: The Export of Indian Labour Overseas”* 1830 – 1920, pp. 58

³⁰ Amarjit Kaur, *“Indian Labour, Labour Standards, and Worker's Health in Burma and Malaya,”* *Modern Asian Studies* 40 (2) (2006), pp. 445.

system was high at that time. An example of that was the indentured migration towards Assam tea plantations, a significant stream of migration that happened inside India, but less known. This migration involved about 2 million people and it took place for several decades between 19th and 20th centuries³¹. Due to these indentured migrations, mortality rates became high.

When the overseas migration in India started, it was primarily composed of male migrant workers. This was so much overwhelming a fact that the British Government was compelled to enact laws to curb gender discrimination in migration. Eventually, this slightly improved the gender share among the migrants by rising the number of female migrants³². At the initial days of migration, it started with a recruiter or *sardar*, whose capability to persuade the innocent migrants to travel long roads toward the destination of migration was important in increasing the number of migrants³³. At the very beginning, this constituted an extreme amount of coercion and the innocent migrants were being compelled to move. This continued for the first few decades from when migrations started. The result of migration, of course, was bonded labour or indentured labour. The coercion at that time was seen as necessary because the migrants were not accustomed to travelling overseas. This created a set of people as emigrants and immigrants. That is to say, a set of people who embarked on from the outgoing port from the ships and another set of people who disembarked from the ships to the destination ports. In 1840s, some legal provisions were made where some “protectors” of immigrants and emigrants were introduced. Their job was to ensure that “no emigrant shall embark without a certificate from the Agent, countersigned by the Protector” leading to a curious phrase that is now imprinted in Indian passports as ‘Emigration Check Not Required’³⁴.

³¹ Behal, Rana P. *“One Hundred Years of Servitude: Political Economy of Tea Plantations in Colonial Assam”* (Tulika, 2014).

³² David Northrup, *“Indentured Labour in the Age of Imperialism, 1834–1922”* (Cambridge University Press, 1995), pp-75

³³ *Ibid*, pp-69

³⁴ Geoghegan, J. *“Note on Emigration from India”* (Calcutta, 1873), pp. 14.

CHAPTER – 3

Migrant Workers of India and International Position

1. Labour Rights -

Social security is a basic and fundamental labour right that is guaranteed by law to those who live by their labour and who do not control the conditions of their labour and living. In terms of social security, these were started during French Revolution. Later it formed the foundation of the French Constitution of 1793.

The International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) of the United Nations is another international instrument. So that they enjoying these rights of self-determination can freely pursue their economic, social, and cultural development³⁵. Our Constitution³⁶ provides for citizenship rights in part II. These are fundamental because they are important for an individual for his holistic humane existence. If minimum wages at the workplace is guaranteed, and not only the subsistence allowance, this will cater to the economic stability of the country as well and also will provide and secure a just and adequate means of livelihood to the working population. These are enshrined in the Directive Principles of State Policies.

2. Labour Standards as per international norms –

The ILO has played a significant role in promoting International Labour Standards formulated at various conferences. ILO passed the convention in June 1976, which was aimed at improving the conditions of labour through discussions with tripartite committees. The preamble of the last ACP-EEC (African Caribbean and the Pacific States) convention signed in 1984. Since its inception, the international labour organization has adopted 181 legally binding conventions and 188 recommendations aimed at improving labour standards across the globe. There are eight core labour standards.

There are four categories such as:

- i) “Right to freedom of Association and collective bargaining”

³⁵ Shyamsundhar, K.R., (2004), *“The Issue of Right to Strike, Report on Four Consultations”*, The Indian Journals of labour Economics, New Delhi.

³⁶ GOI, (1991), *Our Rights and Duties two sides of the same Coin*, Ministry of I and B, printing, Government of India, Calcutta.

- ii) “Elimination of forced labour”
- iii) “Elimination of child labour”
- iv) “Elimination of discrimination in the matter of occupation and wages”

4. Instruments by ILO for Migrant Workers-

There are four migrant worker specific instruments:

- i) “C097 – Migration for Employment Convention (Revised), 1949 (No.97)”³⁷
- ii) “R086 – Migration for Employment Recommendation (Revised), 1949 (No. 86)”³⁸
- iii) “C143 – Migrant Workers (Supplementary Provisions) Convention, 1975 (No. 143)”³⁹
- iv) “R151 – Migrant Workers Recommendation, 1975 (No. 151)”⁴⁰

5. Indian Labour Standards as per ILO –

The Constitution of India is built upon the principle of equality. Hence, labour legislations have fixed the hours and minimum wages of labourers irrespective of their sex to improve their life and living. Also, various social security schemes have been initiated and formulated. But these are for the organized sector workers only. The unorganised sector workers and the informal workers do not have such strong social security protections. The fact is that informal migrant workers form a staggering 92% of the total workforce in our country. And only an estimated 8% falls in the formal or organized sector, which is protected by various labour laws covering Industrial Disputes, Unfair dismissal, trade union rights, wage and working conditions, health, insurance, social security schemes etc⁴¹.

³⁷https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_INSTRUMENT_I D:312242

³⁸ https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_ILO_CODE:R086

³⁹ https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_ILO_CODE:C143

⁴⁰https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_INSTRUMENT_I D:312489

⁴¹ - Singh Parduman, (1997), “*Social Security Systems in Developing Countries*”, Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, New Delhi.

- Singh, Manjit and Iyar, K., (1985), “*Migrant Labourers in Rural Punjab*”, in Patnaik and Pingwaney, (eds.), “*Chains of Servitude Bondage and Slavery in India*”, Sangam books, New Delhi.

- Srivastava, Ravi. S., (1998), “*Migration and the labour market in India*”, The Indian Journals of labour Economics, Vol.41, No.4., October-December,

CHAPTER – 4

Current Status of Indian Migrant Workers

1. Introduction

India is an important country from where people go to work everywhere and also come to work.⁴²⁴³

The reality is that we cannot analyse the international migration trends in india due to the absence of data for this. Data is available only for ECR workers⁴⁴ and to one of the 18 ECR countries.⁴⁵ This means that the data is only available for those workers who register for their respective emigration clearance.

Figure 1: Number of Emigration clearances granted in India (2011–17)⁴⁶

Official data shows 520,938 workers migrated for work legally after completing ECR procedures in 2016, compared to the 784,152 workers who left in 2015. The number for 2017 was 391,024 (emigration clearance obtained via recruitment agents, project employers and direct recruitment, see Figure 1 above). As per the MEA’s

- Thorat, Sukhadeo, (2008), “Labour Market Discrimination Concept, forms and remedies in the Indian Situations”, The Indian Journal of Labour Economics, Vol.51, No.1, January- March

⁴² Sharma, S. and Thapa, D. “Taken for granted: Nepali migration to India”, Working Paper (Kathmandu, Centre for the Study of Labour and Mobility, 2013), and Wadhawan, N. “From rupees to dirhams: Gender, remittances and labour migration from Nepal to the GCC region”, in Jain, P.C. and Oommen, G. (eds): “South Asian migration to the GCC countries” (London, Taylor and Francis, 2016).

⁴³ India hosts 5.2 million migrants as per the UNDESA Migration Trends 2015. Also see ILO Labour Migration Update 2016 for available data on India as a destination.

⁴⁴ Indian nationals who possess ECR passports must obtain emigration clearance if they wish to go abroad. The Government of India can also bring certain occupations into the emigration clearance system, even for those holding ECNR passports.

⁴⁵ According to the MEA website, the 18 ECR countries are the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Qatar, Oman, Kuwait, Bahrain, Libya, Jordan, Yemen, Sudan, South Sudan, Afghanistan, Indonesia, Syria, Lebanon, Thailand, Iraq, and Malaysia.

⁴⁶ <https://emigrate.gov.in/ext/preViewPdfGenRptAction.action>

Annual Report 2016–17, “this drop is explained by the decline in crude oil prices and the resulting economic slowdown in the GCC countries.”⁴⁷

Figure 2: Total emigrants from India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh to GCC countries (2011-17)⁴⁸

2. Migration, skills and employment

Despite decades of economic growth, the overall proportion of informal workers in total employment in India (e.g., “unorganized sector workers plus informal workers in the organized sector”) has remained a constant, at around 92%.⁴⁹ Hence, there exists some degree of informality amongst most of the Indian workforce in their job profiles. “Coupled with a national unemployment rate of 3.4 per cent in 2017-18”,⁵⁰ the opportunities to find formal employment with decent wages and job security are restricted. An ILO study shows that “low-skilled migrant workers are earning approximately 1.5–3 times more in wages in the destination countries (Kuwait, KSA and UAE), even when the wages are compared with the highest rate of minimum wages prevailing among the different Indian states.”⁵¹

“ECR flows might be a very small proportion of the total labour force in India (estimated at nearly 485 million) but in comparison with the annual addition to the labour force in the past two decades (at an average of 7 million to 8 million workers per

⁴⁷ MEA: *Annual report 2016-17* (New Delhi, Government of India, 2017), https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8qM_niyPuIuV1dSYzV2dW45Mmc/view;

⁴⁸ Data for India: <https://emigrate.gov.in/ext/preViewPdfGenRptAction.action>;

data for Pakistan: <http://www.beoe.gov.pk/files/statistics/2017/country.pdf>;

data for Bangladesh: <http://www.bmet.gov.bd/BMET/viewStatReport.action?reportnumber=17>

⁴⁹ ILO: *India labour market update* (2016). Based on NSSO Employment-Unemployment Survey (2011-12)

⁵⁰ ILO: *World employment and social outlook 2017* (Geneva, 2017), http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_541211.pdf

⁵¹ Sasikumar, S.K., and Sharma, S., “*Minimum referral wages for international migrant workers from India: An assessment*” (New Delhi, ILO, 2016), p. 16

year), the labour outflow figures are quite significant, and foreign employment destinations have acted as a crucial safety valve for the Indian labour market”⁵².

There has been a deceleration of employment growth in India before 2011–12, which declined from 2013–14 to 2015–16⁵³. “From 2013–14 to 2015–16, total employment in India reduced by about 0.4 per cent per annum, i.e., an estimated reduction of 3.74 million persons in employment”⁵⁴.

Figure 3: ECR migration from top 10 sending states (2011-17)⁵⁵

The decision to migrate for work is influenced by various factors, especially the availability of employment at home, within the home country and at the migrated place. Wages earned, skill levels, living and working conditions, cost of migration and cultural factors also influence such decisions. Table 3 shows top ten states in India from where people migrate for work purpose. “High poverty levels, unemployment rates and wage differences between source and destination play an important role in influencing migration choices. High-migration zones and specific districts within each of these states usually contribute the bulk of emigrants to the GCC region”⁵⁶.

⁵² Sasikumar, S.K., and Timothy, R., “From India to the Gulf region: Exploring links between labour markets, skills and the migration cycle” (Nepal, GIZ and ILO, 2015)

⁵³ Mehrotra, S. et al: “Explaining employment trends in the Indian economy: 1993–94 to 2011–12”, in *Economic and Political Weekly* (2014, Vol. 49, No. 32), pp. 49–57; and Shaw, A. “Employment trends in India: An overview of NSSO’s 68th round”, in *Economic and Political Weekly* (2013, Vol. 48, No. 42), pp. 23–25

⁵⁴ Abraham, V., “Stagnant employment growth: Last three years may have been the worst”, in *Economic and Political Weekly* (2017, Vol. 52, No. 38), pp. 13–14

⁵⁵ <https://emigrate.gov.in/ext/preViewPdfGenRptAction.action>

⁵⁶ Kumar, K., and Rajan, S.I., “Emigration in the 21st century: Governance, legislation and institutions” (New Delhi, Routledge, 2014)

A crucial factor for determining wages and the migration experience is skills of the workers. “Low-skilled workers, usually ECR migrants, are more vulnerable to wage exploitation and unacceptable living and working conditions. The Indian government has initiated schemes and programmes such as the Skill India initiative to focus on skilled workers and providing training and certification in addition to pre-departure orientation. Steps have also been taken to train and sensitize government officials at the state and central level to enable better migration management”⁵⁷.

Figure 4: State-wise emigration clearances granted (2011-16)⁵⁸

⁵⁷ Rajan, S.I., Bhaskar, T.L.S., and Wadhawan, N., “Predeparture training manual for GCC region and Malaysia” (New Delhi, IOM and MEA, 2017), <https://www.nsdindia.org/sites/default/files/files/PDOT-TOT.pdf>

⁵⁸ <https://emigrate.gov.in/ext/preViewPdfGenRptAction.action>

CHAPTER – 5

Indian Law regarding Migrant Workers

a. International Position -

Now let us discuss some legal aspects regarding migrant workers. There are various types of migrant workers. Some are even international migrant workers. We can classify the migrant workers into two categories, viz, **labour migrants** and **economic migrants**. These are internationally accepted definitions to describe the nature of migration. Let us first analyse these terms before coming to the Indian scenario:

According to **International Organization for Migration (IMO)**⁵⁹, which has created the above-mentioned differentiation, there can be much more types of migrant workers like “**business travellers, contract migrant workers, established migrant workers, highly skilled migrant workers, immigrating investors, project-tied workers, seasonal migrant workers, temporary migrant workers**”. Labour migrants are defined broadly as those who move from their native places for employment. Also, an economic migrant who constitutes a potentially broader group is defined as people including who enter a state to perform economic activities. It may be an investment and/or business-related, business travelling etc.

According to **International Labour Organisation (ILO)**⁶⁰, “a migrant worker is a person who migrates from one country to another (or who has migrated from one country to another) intending to be employed other than his account and includes any person regularly admitted as a migrant for employment.”

The **United Nations Convention on the Protection of the Rights of all Migrant Workers and Members of their Families** defines a migrant worker

⁵⁹ Usher E. Migration and labour. In: Usher E, editor. *“Essentials of migration management: a guide for policy makers and practitioners”*. Geneva: United Nations Publications; 2004.

⁶⁰ ILO background note: the contribution of labour migration to improved development outcomes. Mainstreaming of migration in development policy and integrating migration in the post-2015 UN Development Agenda. Geneva: International Labour Organization; 2015. [5 August 2015]. http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---migrant/documents/genericdocument/wcms_220084.pdf. [Reference list]

as “a person who is to be engaged, is engaged or has been engaged in a remunerated activity in a state of which he or she is not a citizen”⁶¹.

The United Nations Population Division defines irregular migrants (or undocumented migrants) as “individuals who enter a country often in search of employment without the required documents or permits, or who overstay the authorized length of stay in the country”⁶².

b. Indian Position –

In India, we had *The Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979*, enacted for the advantage of migrant labourers. The state of migrant workers was miserable before the enactment of this statute due to the continuation of a colonial era-like bonded labour in parts of our country.

The seasonal labour that was being performed by the migrant workers from other states was being controlled by the *Sardars* and *Khatadars* and was hugely exploitative. The entire payment system was based upon the whims and fancies of the *Sardars* and *Khatadars*. The payments were meagre or almost nil and irregular and there was no standards or minimum wage. There was no fixed work-hour. Once the contractor grabbed the worker, he/ she was being sent to odd places without any idea to return to his/her place.

To curb this and control the Contractors/*Sardars*/*Khatadars*, the 28th session of Labour Ministers’ Conference held at New Delhi on October 26th 1976, it was decided to constitute a small Compact Committee to see the matter and eventually the recommendations of the Compact Committee resulted in the statute. Though it attempted to curb the exploitations faced by the migrant workers and formalise their labour, in the considered opinion of the present researcher, the Act failed to entirely achieve its purpose as it overlooked the millions of unregistered informal migrant workers who did not work under any contractors.

⁶¹ Usher E. Migration and labour. In: Usher E, editor. “*Essentials of migration management: a guide for policy makers and practitioners*”. Geneva: United Nations Publications; 2004.

⁶² Zimmerman C, Kiss L, Hossain M. “*Migration and health: a framework for 21st century policy-making*”. PLoS Med. 2011; **8**(5): e1001034.

The Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979, for the first time, defined **Migrant Workers** in Sec 2(e). It also defines **Contractor** in Sec 2(b) concerning which a worker is being recruited. The Act also defines **Principal Employer** in Sec 2(g) in respect of the establishment where the worker is being employed through the agent or *Khatadar* or *Sardar*. The Act also includes **Workman** in its Definition Section and defines a workman in Sec 2(j). The Act also includes **Wages** having the same meaning as in *The Payment of Wages Act, 1936* in Sec 2(i). All these definitions conform with the definitions given by *The Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act, 1970*, which is also a labour law for the benefit and protection of interests of contract workers.

Also, there is another statute named *The Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act, 2008* which was enacted for the benefit of some other class of workers. These workers were those bunch of people who were self-employed having no agency and/or employer. It defined in Sec 2(b) **Home-based Worker** and conceptualised it. It also conceptualised **Self-employed Worker** in Sec 2(k). It also defined **Unorganised Sector, Unorganised Worker and Wage Worker** respectively in Sec 2(l), Sec 2(m) and Sec 2(n). It is seen that the ambit of this Act providing social security and protection at uneven times is much greater as it encompasses various types of workers. But still, all these Acts and Rules could not save the plight of the migrant workers at the time of nationwide lockdown when it was most required.

Although the two Acts discussed above promise to provide social security for the unorganised and informal migrant workers, there are some other types of workers, migrant, and non-migrant, for whom separate legislation was necessary. Hence, the legislature came with two successive Acts, namely, *Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996* and *Building and Other Construction Workers' Welfare Cess Act, 1996* for various building and other types of construction workers. These two Acts, as their names suggest, are made for the construction workers and various other types of building workers. The first Act is a detailed one providing benefits and protections and security to the building and construction workers. It visualises building and construction workers as **beneficiaries** for obtaining social security u/S 2(b) and defines **building or**

other construction work u/S 2(d). It also conceptualises a **building worker** u/S 2(e). The principal aim of this Act is to create various committees and boards for the welfare and protection of this sector of unorganised workers as well as migrant workers. Chapter II creates Central Advisory Committee⁶³, State Advisory Committees⁶⁴ and Expert Committees⁶⁵. Chapter IV u/S 11 specifies the persons who will be the beneficiaries of the fund created for the welfare of the workers; but for that, the worker requires to be registered under the provisions of Sec 12. But perhaps the most important part of this statute is the creation of State Welfare Boards under Chapter V of the Act. Sec 22 details the functions of the State Welfare Boards. The Act also specifies the hours of work, welfare measures and other conditions of service under Chapter VI. Further, it specifies the Safety and Health Measures to be taken in favour of the building and other construction workers under Chapter VII. Keeping parity with the Industrial Disputes Act, 1948 this Act also creates categories of inspecting staff, such as Director General, Chief Inspector and Inspectors and specifies their duties under Chapter VIII. And under Chapter X has created penal provisions for the contravention of provisions regarding safety measures,⁶⁶ the penalty for failure to give notice of the commencement of the building or other construction work,⁶⁷ penalty for obstructions⁶⁸ and penalty for other offences⁶⁹.

There is another statute mentioned above second to the previous Act discussed, and that was enacted in the same year as that of the *Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996* and it is called *Building and Other Construction Workers' Welfare Cess Act, 1996*. It enables the levy and collection of a cess on the cost of construction acquired by the employers to augment the condition and resources of the Welfare Boards. The chief welfare provisions are given u/S 3 of this Act.

These are some welfare legislations that have been enacted from time to time. But have they been able to protect the migrant workers and other informal workers at

⁶³ Section 3

⁶⁴ Section 4

⁶⁵ Section 5

⁶⁶ Section 47

⁶⁷ Section 48

⁶⁸ Section 49

⁶⁹ Section 50

the time when they needed to be protected most, i.e., at the time of nationwide lockdown due to the Covid-19 pandemic? We will see that later.

Mention must be made at this point that the statutes discussed above have now been replaced by new codes. All the social security legislation that has been discussed, have been consolidated into ***The Code on Social Security, 2020***. This code is for all the workers – be they employed in organised or unorganised sectors. It includes:

- a. *The Employees' Compensation Act, 1923*
- b. *The Employees' State Insurance Act, 1948*
- c. *The Employees' Provident Funds and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952*
- d. *The Employment Exchanges (Compulsory Notification of Vacancies) Act 1959*
- e. *The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961*
- f. *The Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972*
- g. *The Cine Workers Welfare Fund Act, 1981*
- h. *The Building and Other Construction Workers Welfare Cess Act, 1996*
- i. *Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act 2008.*

Another new code, namely, ***The Occupational Safety, Health and Working Conditions Code, 2020*** amalgamated the following legislations. It aims at regulating the health and safety conditions of the workers in all sectors and establishments with ten or more workers.

- a. *The Factories Act, 1948*
- b. *The Plantations Labour Act, 1951*
- c. *The Mines Act, 1952*
- d. *The Working Journalists and other Newspaper Employees (Conditions of Service and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act, 1955*
- e. *The Working Journalists (Fixation of Rates of Wages) Act, 1958*
- f. *The Motor Transport Workers Act, 1961*
- g. *The Beedi and Cigar Workers (Conditions of Employment) Act, 1966*
- h. *The Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act, 1970*
- i. *The Sales Promotion Employees (Condition of Service) Act, 1976*
- j. *The Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979*

- k. *The Cine Workers and Cinema Theatre Workers Act, 1981*
- l. *The Dock Workers (Safety, Health and Welfare) Act, 1986*
- m. *The Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996*

The ***Code on Wages, 2019*** is another code passed by the Parliament by amalgamating four labour legislation which will now control the wages and payments of a worker in all sectors:

- a. *Payment of Wages Act, 1936*
- b. *The Minimum Wages Act, 1948*
- c. *The Payment of Bonus Act, 1965*
- d. *The Equal Remuneration Act, 1976*

The ***Industrial Relations Code, 2020*** is another code that was enacted by the Parliament by consolidating three labour law legislations. This code aims to improve the business environment by reducing the labour compliance burden by the industries.

- a. *The Industrial Disputes Act, 1947*
- b. *The Trade Unions Act, 1926*
- c. *The Industrial Employment (Standing Orders) Act, 1946*

CHAPTER – 6

Analysis of some other relevant legislations

1. *Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993*

Human Rights are those inalienable rights that are enjoyed by us due to the reason of our being human. This right and the respective Act originate from the ICCPR and ICESCR which were adopted by the General Assembly of UN in 1966. India is a party and a signatory to these international instruments, and because Human Rights are substantially protected by our Constitution, the Parliament in 1993 enacted the ***Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993***. The Act has been legislated to prevent the violation of Human Rights by establishing State and National Human Rights Commissions, which have immense powers.

Now let us come to the connection between Human Rights law and the plight of the migrant workers during the nationwide lockdown. It is a fact that the sudden nationwide lockdown announced by our Prime Minister had unequal effects on different strata of our society. For the migrant workers, it came as devastating. They are marginalised communities in our country and before they came out in large numbers in streets in sheer desperation to return to their houses as a result of lockdown, we had forgotten them. They faced a sudden lack of livelihood, lack of food, shelter, health, and other basic subsistence crisis. Usually, they rent a house in their place of work and live there with many inmates. So, they couldn't keep social distance as required to contain the virus. Also, their work and hence payment was stopped but their landlord did not stop demanding fares of their houses. They had no money even to feed their family and had to pay thousands for bus or train tickets in their return to their native places. Some migrant workers were arrested and some were found inside a moving tanker. Some migrants crossed thousands of kilometres by simply walking barefoot and many died *en route*. Some were sleeping on the railway tracks as the tracks were easiest to get knowing the road towards home. They were overrun by a goods train and died on the tracks. Those who were lucky enough to reach their village were faced by the village administration and other local and stigmatized for carrying the disease from the cities. They were denied basic subsistence and had to isolate themselves from society.

Some were not lucky enough to make themselves isolated in their own house, they had to take shelter outside the village or under large trees for 14 days.

After a roar of critiques by the opposition parties and the civil society, the Central Government arranged trains for them but the irony was that they had to pay for their return and the trains seldom reached their targeted destinations. Also, the trains were devoid of any basic services or food or drinking water. Many people died inside the train from the extreme exhaustion of journeying long paths without food and water. These are the violations of the State and Central Governments which went on unnoticed when the support of the welfare state was the most necessary.

2. Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005

This Act was conceptualised for the first time by P.V. Narsimha Rao in 1991. Eventually, it was accepted by the Parliament and the law set in motion. 2005 onwards. This Act is executed and implement through Gram Panchayats. The initial aim of MGNREGA or NREGA was to assuage livelihood of rural population by arranging a hundred-days of guaranteed simple and unskilled wage labour in a given financial year. It promised to do so for those households which had adult members and willing to do unskilled manual labour. It provided job cards to those for joining the scheme. The second objective of MGNREGA is to create permanent and durable assents like roads, ponds, canals, wells etc. The employment is to provide within 5 kilometres distance of the job cardholder and the payment is to be cleared within 15 days of completion of the work, lest they will have to be paid unemployment allowance. This is truly welfare legislation.

This Act is also closely connected to the present migrant worker crisis during the nationwide lockdown. During the starting of lockdown in 2020, an estimated 20 to 30 million migrant workers returned to their homes in villages. They were all out of money, hence desperately needed money to feed themselves and their families. They tried farming, but farming at the time of lockdown yielded much less earning. The government estimated that between April and September 2020, 8.3 million new NREGA job cards⁷⁰ were issued. But the general population was not that lucky. A 17%

⁷⁰ <https://idronline.org/nrega-performance-in-lockdown-social-protection-migrants/>

of the applicants did not get job cards. The Finance Ministry announced an additional Rs. 40000 crores to boost India's rural NREGA programme in May 2020⁷¹.

3. Right of the Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009

The Right to Education is a Constitutional Right emanating from the 22nd amendment to the Constitution in 2002, whereby Article 21A⁷² was introduced in the body of the Constitution. It provides for the right of the children from 6-14 years of age to free and compulsory education, i.e., till the completion of their elementary education. The burden is on the State to provide them with free and compulsory education. It makes provisions for a non-admitted child to be admitted compulsorily to a class that is suitable for his/her age group. It was approved in May 2009 and enacted in the same year.

This Act is also connected to our present study as the children of the migrant workers are in deep danger as there have no schooling sessions during the last one and half years, and classroom teaching is stopped. Many of the children have already left out of the schooling system due to the economic burden of their family and most probably will not return to the system of education in future. Since the burden of providing free and compulsory education lies upon the State, it has failed the students during this nationwide lockdown as some of them are enrolled in the place of working of their parents, some are enrolled in the schools of their villages. Those enrolled in the places of working of their parents are left out of the schooling system as their parents have mostly moved to their native lands and even if they have returned to their old working places during the unlocking, they have not brought their children with them as the schools are closed. Also, even if their parents collect uncooked MDM from schools, it does not reach the targeted children as they are in far off places from their parents. Although many private educational institutions have started sessions of "online class", and a small number of government schools have also started the same, the children at the government schools are left far behind as they or their parents do not possess smartphones or do not have access to free and high-speed internet required for the online classes. This huge **digital gap** has also failed the purposes of the Right to

⁷¹ <https://thewire.in/rights/covid-19-lockdown-nrega-centre-boost-budget>

⁷² *Art. 21A - The State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of six to fourteen years in such manner as the State may, by law, determine*

Education Act. Also, there are large **gender gaps** in the schooling system as the girls in the family are the last ones who get going to the schools, chiefly in the rural areas. The nationwide lockdown has aggravated the plight of the girl students more and more as schools are closed and even if they re-open, the school drop-out rate for the girl students most probably will be much greater than that of boy students.

4. *National Food Security Act, 2013*

This Act may be called the Right to Food Act also. It was introduced in the Parliament on 22.12.2011, then promulgated through Presidential ordinance on 05.07.2013 and eventually enacted as an Act on 12.09.2013. This Act integrates three Governmental schemes long in effect, viz., a) *Public Distribution System* (PDS, started in January 1945 during the Second World War, and finally launched in the present form in June 1947. The concept of rationing though dates to 1940 during the infamous *Bengal Famine*), b) *Integrated Child Development Services* (ICDS, started on 02.10.1975) and c) *Midday Meal Scheme* (MDM, started in 1995). Among these three, the ICDS and MDM are executed through Government Schools and the *Tenth Five-year Plan* linked ICDS to *Anganwadi* centres located mainly in rural areas, and the PDS is executed through ration shops.

The connections of this Act and these schemes to the plight of the migrant workers are manifold. Since they are migrant workers, they do not possess ration cards at their place of work where they have been stranded due to the nationwide lockdown, they could not get easy access to free rations and safe drinking water. Many the migrant workers are daily wage-earners and so they couldn't buy their foods daily and feed themselves and their family which included child and infirm elderly people. India has ratified the UNCRC or the *United Nations Convention on The Rights of Child*, has failed the children of those migrant workers. Also, since last one year and more, all the schools are closed and hence the distribution of cooked MDM directly to the children is also stopped. Providing the family with uncooked MDM does not fully appreciate the spirit of the MDM. Hence, the migrant workers have been deprived of the right to food in this way.

CHAPTER – 7

Lockdown in India and the legal sanction behind it

Inter arma enim silent lēgēs

(In times of war, the law falls silent)

- Pro Milone, Cicero⁷³

“Lockdown”, “curfew” etc are not legal terms. They are used here and there without any standards. In 1824, the US Supreme Court in an *en banc* sitting by the Chief Justice ordered that the State had blanket powers to enact quarantine laws during health emergencies and pandemics. The world has since then viewed many such pandemics, but no one questioned the authority of the State to impose quarantines and/or lockdowns. The method of quarantine happens to be the oldest method to stop and contain the spread of any infectious disease, may that be any bacterial or any viral disease. It has legal sanctions all over the world. Since time immemorial, societies have practised isolations and quarantines during the outbreak of a disease. And not to mention that all these methods of quarantines and lockdowns hitherto have been forcible ones. Although quarantining the patient for the benefit of the whole society to stop the spread of any disease is a medically approved method. But the treatment of the patient is of far greater importance than that.

The first law on medical isolation was passed in 1377⁷⁴ when the plague was raging in European countries. Detention for medical reasons was justified and disobedience was punishable. This law prescribed an isolation period of 30 days and it was called *trentino*. When the duration of isolation was extended for 40 days, it was referred to as *quadraginta*. Hence, the term quarantine.

Now if we come to modern times, we are having a pandemic after 100 years. Within this period our medical science has developed to an extreme level and still, we are having forced lockdowns and quarantine regimes. And that without promulgation of any emergency. But during lockdowns, some of our Fundamental Rights are being

⁷³ “For among arms, the laws are silent”; but is more popularly rendered as “In times of war, the law falls silent”. <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/cicero/milo.shtml>

⁷⁴ <https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/lead/quarantine-and-the-law/article31241185.ece>

suspended. For example, Article 19(1)b⁷⁵ and 19(1)d⁷⁶ are suspended without having declared any emergency. This is an unprecedented situation without having any parallel in the constitutional history of independent India. Never in the collective history of this country after independence can this phenomenon be traced that we are not free to move anywhere in the country as per our wish. Not only that, markets, shops, malls, pubs, etc have all been closed for a considerable period. During this period of lockdown, lots of people have lost their job, be it salaried or small-scale businesses. Thus, lockdown without having any clear sanction in our Constitution has wreaked havoc in our social, economic, and personal lives. Let us now discuss in brief the laws which are being used to declare nationwide lockdowns.

Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897

This is an Act from antiquity. The British colonial rulers enacted this statute 123 years ago to combat the spread of the “*Bubonic Plague*”⁷⁷, but the Act was specifically created more to tackle the native Indians and save the British officers. It is of utter surprise that even after more than one hundred years, we have only this Act to combat a comparatively newer pandemic caused by Coronavirus. Whereas we had the clues of a similar kind of disease way back in 2003, called SARS or “*Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome*”⁷⁸, we did not care about creating any statutes or rules to combat diseases like these. So, we are left with nothing but an archaic law of just 4 (four) sections at our disposal to combat the spread of a highly contagious disease like SARS-CoV-2. The sanction behind the present-era lockdown emanates from this Act. The term “lockdown” is though not present in the Act itself, but a careful reading of Section 2⁷⁹ reveals that there has been given a blanket discretion to the Government to use state

⁷⁵ *to assemble peaceably and without arms;*

⁷⁶ *to move freely throughout the territory of India;*

⁷⁷ <https://www.bbc.com/news/health-53305721>

⁷⁸ <https://www.cdc.gov/sars/index.html>

⁷⁹ Power to take special measures and prescribe regulations as to dangerous epidemic disease.—(1) *When at any time the [State Government] is satisfied that [the State] or any part thereof is visited by, or threatened with, an outbreak of any dangerous epidemic disease, the [State Government], if [it] thinks that the ordinary provisions of the law for the time being in force are insufficient for the purpose, may take, or require or empower any person to take, such measures and, by public notice, prescribe such temporary regulations to be observed by the public or by any person or class of persons as [it] shall deem necessary to prevent the outbreak of such disease or the spread thereof, and may determine in what manner and by whom any expenses incurred (including compensation if any) shall be defrayed.*

powers if it thinks so. And that exactly has been the case in present-era lockdown measures. Some states have even enacted their statutes, like

- a) The Delhi Epidemic Diseases COVID 19 Regulations, 2020⁸⁰;
- b) *The Maharashtra Epidemic Diseases COVID-19 Regulations, 2020*⁸¹;
- c) *The Punjab Epidemic Diseases COVID-19 Regulations, 2020*⁸²;
- d) The Himachal Pradesh Epidemic Disease (COVID-19) Regulations, 2020⁸³;
- e) *The West Bengal Epidemic Disease, COVID-19 Regulations, 2020*⁸⁴.

Now if we come to Section 3 of the Principal Act⁸⁵, we find that a provision of penalty has been given in that section which will come under IPC, Section 188, that the subject population is left at the mercy of administrative and beaurocratic whims, and this is construed to be the legal and legitimate process for combating pandemic of this stature.

It is to be noted that the terms *quarantine* and *isolation* were there in use under some different statutes like ***Indian Aircraft (Public Health) Rules, 1954*** and ***Indian Port Health Rules, 1955***.

Last but not the least, I must make a mention of the EDA Section 4 here which expressly states that “*No suit or other legal proceeding shall lie against any person for anything done or in good faith intended to be done under this Act*”. This is the worst part of this colonial Act, where no officer of the administration, irrespective of his/her rank and file, can’t be judicially tried for the deeds h/she has done “*in good faith*” and under the guise of this Act. Hence the intervention of the judiciary is being kept in

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[http://health.delhigovt.nic.in/wps/wcm/connect/c05a8d804d883d25974cf7982ee7a5c7/NED+Act.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&lmod=-754584952&CACHEID=c05a8d804d883d25974cf7982ee7a5c7#:~:text=These%20regulations%20may%20be%20called.COVID%2D19%20Regulations%2C%202020.&text=4..\(Corona%20Virus%20Disease%202019\)](http://health.delhigovt.nic.in/wps/wcm/connect/c05a8d804d883d25974cf7982ee7a5c7/NED+Act.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&lmod=-754584952&CACHEID=c05a8d804d883d25974cf7982ee7a5c7#:~:text=These%20regulations%20may%20be%20called.COVID%2D19%20Regulations%2C%202020.&text=4..(Corona%20Virus%20Disease%202019))

⁸¹

<https://www.maharashtra.gov.in/Site/Upload/Acts%20Rules/Marathi/notification%2031%2008%202020.pdf>

⁸²

<http://www.diprpunjab.gov.in/?q=content/punjab-govt-announces-emergency-measures-combat-coronavirus-menace#:~:text=The%20Cabinet%20approved%20the%20Punjab,of%20the%20Epidemic%20Disease%20Act.&text=Spread%20of%20any%20rumors%20or,the%20notification%2C%20said%20the%20spokesperson>

⁸³ <http://dhsr.hp.gov.in/?q=order-himachal-pradesh-epidemic-disease-covid-19-regulation-2020>

⁸⁴

https://www.wbhealth.gov.in/uploaded_files/corona/Epidemic_Disease_Regulation_West_Bengal.pdf

⁸⁵ *The Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897* (Act No. 3 OF 1897)

abeyance in this case the myth of an independent judiciary falls short here and the entire event of lockdown becomes a mockery of the judicial and justice system.

Disaster Management Act, 2005

This is not an Act to combat with or creating effective management plans in respect of any pandemic or even epidemic. It is an Act to create management policies regarding any natural calamities. The definition of “disaster” has been given u/S 2(d)⁸⁶ of the Act, and there is no mention of any diseases. On 14th March 2020, the Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA) decided that COVID-19 will be treated as a ***notified disaster*** under the *Disaster Management Act, 2005*. This decision made the State Governments use more from the State Disaster Response Fund (SDRF) for the COVID-19 pandemic. The use of DMA by the Centre made the NDMA or the **National Disaster Management Authority** the sole authority to publish directions and S.O.P.s (Standard Operating Protocols) regarding fighting the COVID-19 pandemic. If COVID-19 were not declared as a notified disaster, the SDRF funds could not have been utilized for combating the pandemic as this fund was made for cyclones, droughts, tsunamis, hailstorms, landslides, avalanches, and pest attacks. In its document named “Disaster Management in India”, the MHA made a mention of the High-Power Committee on Disaster Management, which was constituted in 1999. Let us now briefly concentrate on this committee.

High Power Committee on Disaster Management, 1999

A “High-Power Committee (HPC)” was constituted in August 1999 under the chairmanship of Shri J.C. Pant. The members of this committee were from Ministries, States, NGOs, and experts from different fields. Before the enactment of the *National Disaster Management Act, 2005* this was the first attempt in our country to make a comprehensive, systematic, and holistic approach towards combating disasters. Following is the conceptual framework of the HPC⁸⁷:

⁸⁶ “disaster” means a catastrophe, mishap, calamity, or grave occurrence in any area, arising from natural or man-made causes, or by accident or negligence which results in substantial loss of life or human suffering or damage to, and destruction of, property, or damage to, or degradation of, environment, and is of such a nature or magnitude as to beyond the coping capacity of the community of the affected area.

⁸⁷ Reproduced from High Power Committee on Disaster Management website: https://www.preventionweb.net/files/1633_ch3.pdf

The HPC identified 31 disasters and categorised them under five sub-groups⁸⁸:

- a) “Sub-Group I – Water and Climate-Related Disasters”
- b) “Sub-Group II – Geological Disasters”
- c) “Sub-Group III – Chemical/Industrial/Nuclear Disasters”
- d) “Sub-Group IV – Accident-Related Disasters”
- e) “Sub-Group V – Biological Disasters”

It took into consideration some international practices, viz, “United Nations System”, “United States of America System”, “Bangladesh System”, “Australian System”, “Japanese System”, “SUMA-WHO/PAHO”, “Incident Command System”, “HAZUS, RADIUS, GESI”.

Among the Biological Disasters, it mentioned:

- a) “Biological Disasters and Epidemics”
- b) “Pest Attacks”
- c) “Cattle Epidemics”
- d) “Food Poisoning”

It is to be noted that the situation has not been changed much since then, and yet, the Central Government has not come up with any comprehensive planning to combat a pandemic like COVID-19 to date.

In short, the planning to combat the COVID-19 pandemic in India solely rests on EDA, DMA, IPC, and CrPC. These are the legal backings behind the imposition of a nationwide lockdown.

⁸⁸ https://nidm.gov.in/pdf/pubs/hpc_report.pdf

CHAPTER – 8

COVID-19 Crisis, Migrant Workers, and Indian State's Response

Yaad kijiye, Mahabharat ka yuddh 18 din mein jeeta gaya tha. Aaj Corona ke khilaf jo yuddh pura desh lad raha hai, usme 21 din laagne wale hain. Humara prayas hai isse 21 din mein jeet liya jaaye. Mahabharat ke yuddh ke samay Bhagwan Sri Krishna Maharathi the; saarhi the. Aaj 130 crore maha-rathiwon ke balbute par humme Corona ke khilaf iss ladai ko jeetna hai.

- Prime Minister Narendra Modi

Addressing his Parliamentary Constituency

on March 25, 2020⁸⁹

Introduction

On 24th March 2020, PM Narendra Modi announced a nationwide lockdown giving people only four hours to prepare for the suspension of all movements in and around the country. He though left no remark on why the international airports were not shut down or any quarantine measures had not been taken there. The next day. He, from his Parliamentary Constituency *Varanasi*, invoked the *Mahabharata* and its 18-day battle as if it were a historical fact rather than fiction and in his typically stylised manner announced that the battle against Corona will be won in twenty-one days through a stringent lockdown. *The Guardian* on 4th July 2020 commented that “*India had one of the world’s strictest lockdowns*”⁹⁰.

The first case of coronavirus in India was reported on 30th January 2020.⁹¹ On that day, globally the numbers had already reached thousands. It was imminent that the numbers in India would increase by leaps and bounds if nothing is done to contain the spread. Yet in India, the minimum safeguards like quarantining in Airports or any screening mechanisms were not implemented. On March 13th, 2020 the Indian Government officially stated that the Coronavirus crisis was not a public health

⁸⁹ <https://theprint.in/india/mahabharata-war-won-in-18-days-but-fight-against-coronavirus-will-take-21-days-says-modi/388267/>

⁹⁰ <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/jul/04/india-lockdowns-cases-rising->
⁹¹ <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/indias-first-coronavirus-infection-confirmed-in-kerala/article30691004.ece>

emergency in India⁹². And within less than a fortnight, the Indian Government dramatically announced a nationwide lockdown and stoppage of all inland movements! This betrays the myopic vision of the Indian Government about the COVID-19 pandemic and its unwillingness to act as a welfare state anymore for the millions of migrant workers or most of the workforce of this country.

After the nationwide lockdown was announced, we saw some horrific visuals like the migrant workers coming out of their rented houses in proportions of millions and congregate at the bus terminuses and railway stations hoping to find some means to return to their homes in faraway villages because their livelihood at the cities had stopped due to the lockdown, and the State did not take any responsibility to compensate them. It only came with a policy of *social distancing to combat the virus* and that social distancing doesn't feed anybody or help somebody to find jobs.

Condition of Migrant Workers in India before the Lockdown

Far-reaching shifts in economic policies from the beginning of the 1990s boosted the Indian economy but also led to inequality and vulnerability for disadvantaged groups and communities. Last thirty years witnessed fundamental changes in the nature, character and modus operandi of the Indian state, as new financial measures and policies were introduced depending on the contemporary global development levels⁹³.

“With economic globalisation and its concomitant objectives and agenda, changes in systems of welfare were introduced. Welfare states were an integral feature of advanced liberal economies in the 20th century after the two world wars, when social protection networks were established to protect the working class from fluctuating incomes, thus enabling economic and political stability”⁹⁴. “Social policy that compensated for the harmful consequences of economic development in the last century remains even more relevant in times of liberalisation and the international flow of capital and labour”⁹⁵. Instead, in the wealthier countries, model welfare states have

⁹² <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/coronavirus-outbreak-union-health-ministry-press-conference-in-new-delhi/article31061163.ece>

⁹³ Jha, M. K., (2012). “*State, space and political subjects: A case of special economic zones*”. The Indian Journal of Social Work, 73(2), 157–176.

⁹⁴ Swank, D., & Betz, H., (2003). “Globalization, the welfare state and right-wing populism in Western Europe”. Socio-economic Review, 1, 215–245

⁹⁵ *ibid*

shrunk, while in emerging economies with a large, deprived population, social protection programmes attempted to secure targeted and conditional protection for vulnerable population groups. “Social policy was to play a residual role to support flexible labour market and competitive economy in the global marketplace”⁹⁶. “In India, redistributive policies are linked to democratic electoral politics, and the economic transition created new pressures to address entrenched poverty and inequalities”⁹⁷. Social and economic inequalities in India follow the contours of caste, gender, tribe, religion and regional divisions. “Social welfare policies have tried to address these varied aspects of vulnerability through poverty alleviation programmes since the 1980s”⁹⁸. Despite these efforts, most people (outside of the small formal sector) remain dependent on family, community, agriculture and the informal economy for income, livelihood and social protection to cope with life course risks and economic downturns. They also rely on expensive private healthcare and education due to inadequate public services. This situation creates many challenges for social policy over time, such as which risks should be prioritised, which sections of the population should be covered, how much should be spent and, most importantly, what should be the minimum level of protection that the state should provide.

“The 2017–18 labour force survey counts 415 million informal workers in India, 90 per cent of the total workforce, and 28 million rural-to-urban workers— consisting of small farmers, labourers, shepherds, fisherfolk, weavers and artisans, forest gatherers, food processors, construction labourers and tradesmen, domestic workers, manufacturing workers (factories, workshops, homes), street vendors, transport workers and waste pickers”⁹⁹. They bear multiple deprivations and injustices due to the nature and character of their employment conditions. “According to the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) of 2017–18, for instance, more than 70 per cent of the

⁹⁶ Jessop, B., (2004). “*Hollowing out the ‘nation state’ and multi-level governance*”. In P. Kennett (ed), *A handbook of comparative social policy* (pp. 1–11). Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.

Kennett, P., (Ed.) (2004). “*Introduction: The changing context of comparative social policy*”. *A handbook of comparative social policy* (pp 1–11). UK: Edward Elgar.

⁹⁷ Bardhan, P., (2009). “*Notes on the political economy of India’s tortuous transition*”. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 44(49), 31–36.

⁹⁸ Nayak, R., Saxena, N. C., & Farrington, J., (2002). “*Reaching the poor: The influence of policy and administrative processes on the implementation of government poverty schemes in India*” (ODI Working Paper 175). Retrieved from <https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/100451/wp175.pdf>

⁹⁹ Chen, M. (2020). “*To die from hunger or the virus. An all too real dilemma for the poor in India and elsewhere*”. Retrieved from <https://www.wider.unu.edu/publication/diehunger-or-virus>

workers in the non-agricultural sector with a regular salary—most of them migrants—did not have a written job contract, about 55 per cent were not eligible for paid leave, and 50 per cent did not have any social security benefits”¹⁰⁰.

In 2006, a national committee found that a majority of this group lived in poverty and lacked legal security of work. The commission had recommended the setting up of the National Social Security and Welfare Fund and social security and welfare boards¹⁰¹. The social legislation from this exercise, *The Unorganised Worker’s Social Security Act, 2008*, never emerged as a viable instrument due to lack of dedicated funds and absence of political support¹⁰². In the absence of formal recognition of informal workers’ needs and rights and avenues to protect them, the government would urgently need to combine the two generations of welfare and poverty relief measures—a combination of transfers in cash and kind, public works and free health services—to address the present condition. The unfolding migrant situation, deemed an unprecedented humanitarian crisis, requires urgent recognition of the gaps in social protection for people who carry the weight but not so much the rewards of the Indian economy.

Lockdown Experiences for the Migrant Workers

Due to the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic, a sudden proclamation of a nationwide lockdown was made in force and then extended for several times thereafter. The first of such phase started from 24th March, 2020 and ended on 31st May, 2020. The second of such lockdown started from 18th May. All this was supposed to started for breaking the chain of transmission. This caused a large hue and cry among millions of migrant workers in India’s big cities and town as they were given a time of only 4 hours to prepare for transit to their native places. Also, the announcement made them instantly jobless. The situation put the returning migrant workers into so much panick

¹⁰⁰ Government of India. (2019). Periodic labour force survey 2017–18. Retrieved from http://www.mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/Annual%20Report%2C%20PLFS%2017-18_31052019.pdf

¹⁰¹ Kannan, K., Srivastava, R., & Sengupta, A., (2006). A major national initiative. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 41(32), 3477–3480. Retrieved June 4, 2020 from www.jstor.org/stable/4418556

¹⁰² Dutta, T., & Pal, P., (2012). “*Politics overpowering welfare: Unorganised Workers’ Social Security Act 2008*”. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 47(7), 26–30. Retrieved from www.jstor.org/stable/41419792

that they started to gather at the bus stops with a hope to find a seat in the busses, but without any success.

On 14 April last year, an IMF blog remarked that the quarantine and social distancing practices had resulted in an enormous downfall in all economic activities, and it pointed that since the great depression of 1929, it was the worst economic setback of the history.¹⁰³ According to a CMIE report¹⁰⁴, India's lockdown order led to a jump in the unemployment rate from 21% - 26% in middle of the month of April and a weekly decline in labour market participation (*The Economic Times*, 2020, April 29). CMIE data show that the unemployment rate increased from 7.03 per cent in May 2019 to 23.98 per cent on 2 May 2020 (Centre for Monitoring of Indian Economy, 2020).

There are ample media reports and TV footages that show the miserable conditions of the migrant workers who tried on their own to return to their home after the announcement of the nation-wide lockdown. These people include several informal sector workers like domestic service, construction work and daily earners from the cooking services in hotels. The estimated number of these people are in the range of 60,000—70,000 people.¹⁰⁵ These included the states of Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh.

COVID-19 Relief Measures – were they sufficient?

On 26th March, the Finance Ministry declared a relief package for the poor who were affected by COVID-19. This included free foodgrains, LPG, cash for three months and insurance coverage. In April, the government announced that 330 million poor people have been helped with cash transfers amounting to Rs. 312350 million under PMGKY; also, it stated that, Rs. 100,000 million has been transferred to 200 million women holding special Jan- Dhan accounts (Rs. 500 per person), Rs. 14050 million was provided under pension schemes to 28.2 million people; Rs. 161460 million to 80 million registered farmers under PM-KISAN; and Rs. 34970 million support to 21.7 million building and construction workers. Under the PMGKY, 392.7 million

¹⁰³ Gopinath, G., (2020). “*The great lockdown: The worst economic downturn since the great depression*”. Retrieved from <https://blogs.imf.org/2020/04/14/the-great-lockdownworst-economic-downturn-since-the-great-depression/>

¹⁰⁴ Centre for Monitoring of Indian Economy (CMIE). (2020). “*Unemployment rate in India*”. Retrieved from <https://unemploymentinindia.cmie.com/>

¹⁰⁵ *ibid*

people received free food grains, and 26.6 million LPG cylinders were distributed under the PMUY.

These were not something novel. These were regular relief disbursements which were dues to eligible groups and did not account for the new devastation. These made the miserly conditions of the needy and poor people not much better as it was advertised.¹⁰⁶

These transfers amounted to less than 0.8 per cent of the GDP and only 5.6 per cent of the central government's planned financial outlay for 2020—21. Cash transfers to Jan-Dhan accounts amount to less than Rs. 17 per household and Rs. 4 (USD 0.05) per person per day¹⁰⁷. Moreover, migrant workers unable to return home and those who are not ration cardholders at the destination would not benefit from additional free food grains under the PDS.

It is to be noted that under BOCWWB, an Act to cater to the needs of the building and other construction workers, to get the benefit of the Act, the workers are to be registered and registration requires at least 90 days of work in the previous year. Most states do not register migrants, and registration is not portable. This is the present scenario of the welfare legislations in our country.

¹⁰⁶ Bajaj, A., Datt, G., Lata, G., Islam, A., Jayasuriya, S., Maitra, P., ... Ray, R., (2020, April 2). “*Nine concerns about the Centre's 1.7 lakh crore package*”. Retrieved from <https://thewire.in/government/covid-19-india-government-package>

¹⁰⁷ *ibid*

CHAPTER – 9

Judicial Response towards the Migrant Workers Crisis

Central Government in Denial Mode

On 14th March 2020, the Narendra Modi-led NDA Government's Labour and employment minister was giving replies to the questions asked by several MPs on the first day of the Monsoon Session of the Parliament. Let us quote the conversation inside the Lok Sabha as it happened¹⁰⁸:

“Answers to Unstarred Question No. 174 Regarding the Return of Migrant Workers to Their Hometowns to be answered on 14.09.2020

Will the Minister of LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT be pleased to state -

a) Whether the Government has the data of migrant workers who returned to their states from various states during the national lockdown period and if so, the details thereof, State-wise -

Government Response: *A statement is enclosed.*

b) The number of such labourers died/ injured during migration to their native places due to such lockdown, State/ UT-wise -

Government Response: *No such data is available.*

c) Whether the Government has provided any compensation/economic assistance to the victims' family and if so, the details thereof -

Government response: *No such data is available.”*

It is not hard to decipher from the above that the Central Government completely denied the fact that nearly thousands of migrant workers died on-road and crores lost their job. But the Government did not keep any data of such. Thus, the Government was in denial mode – it denied the migrant workers' plight and their hardships due to and during the nationwide lockdown. Thus, it evaded its responsibility under the *Inter-State Migrant Workmen Act, 1979* which included compensation for the migrant workers in crisis. Let us not forget that till July 4 2020, almost a thousand migrant workers had died on road returning to their homes whether by foot or by *Shramik Special Trains*.

¹⁰⁸ <https://thewire.in/rights/migrant-workers-no-data-centre-covid-19-lockdown-deaths-distress-swan>

Deaths due to Lockdown in India as of 4 July 2020

***Total including Unclassified 971**

full dataset: <http://thej.in/go/lockdown>
queries: trackinglockdowndeaths@gmail.com

Source: thej.in/go/lockdown¹⁰⁹

Data on deaths of migrants

Cause of Deaths	Number of Deaths (numbers determined as of 4/7/2020)
Starvation and Financial Distress (Combined)	216
Lack of Medical Care	77
Road or Train Accidents	209
Deaths in Shramik Trains	96
Suicides	133
Deaths in Quarantine Centers	49
Lockdown associated Crimes	18
Police Brutality	12
Alcohol Withdrawal Related	49
Exhaustion	48
Unclassified	65
TOTAL	971

Source: thej.in/go/lockdown¹¹⁰

¹⁰⁹ <https://thewire.in/labour/migrant-labourers-data-deaths-numbers>

¹¹⁰ <https://thewire.in/rights/migrant-workers-no-data-centre-covid-19-lockdown-deaths-distress-swan>

These are the data that were kept voluntarily by *pro bono* individuals. From this data, it can be said that this is the tip of the iceberg. Also, if we closely follow the CMIE website¹¹¹, it will reveal that there are huge job losses during the period of lockdown and the unemployment rates are still on increase. But the Indian Government, making a paradigm shift of its role as a welfare state, has not done anything to alleviate the situation for the migrant workers except issuing S.O.P.s and other directives and making announcements that lead to nowhere.

Supreme Court on the issue of Migrant Workers' Crisis

On 24th March 2020, Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced a nationwide lockdown starting from midnight of that day. No one could ever imagine the forthcoming plight and harsh reality in store for millions of migrant workers who work in various cities, away from their homes, mostly in villages. When they started coming out from their rented houses, we realized the massacre that has been done by the topmost administrator of this country.

On 30th March 2020, i.e., 6 days after the announcement of lockdown, a petition was filed in the Supreme Court *pro bono*. Thereafter, many such petitions have been filed and hence I will discuss the matter in chronological order.

30th March, 2020: Alakh Alok Srivastava v. Union of India¹¹²

This was a PIL filed by an advocate of the Supreme Court seeking the following relief from the court:

“direct the local administration/ police authorities across India to immediately identify such moving/ stranded migrant workers and to immediately shift them to the nearest government shelter homes/ accommodations with proper food, water, medicines and under medical supervision, in a dignified manner, till the present Coronavirus Lockdown continues.”¹¹³

¹¹¹ <https://www.cmie.com/kommon/bin/sr.php?kall=warticle&dt=2021-05-4%2011:01:18&msec=696>

¹¹² *Alakh Alok Srivastava v. Union of India*, 2020 SC 345

¹¹³ <https://www.scobserver.in/beyond-the-court/covid-coverage-migrant-labourers-30th-march-2020>

31st March, 2020: Alakh Alok Srivastava v. Union of India

In its reply to the previous day's hearing, the Union filed an affidavit containing a status report, including the following¹¹⁴:

- “an expert group constituted under Dr Vinod Paul, Member, NITI Aayog, to guide the prevention of the spread of the virus”;
- “announcement of a relief package totalling Rs.1.70 lakh crore under Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Yojana”;
- “direction to the District Collectors/Magistrates to ensure that medical tests were done and the migrant labourers provided with basic amenities like food, clean drinking water, medicines, etc. in the shelter homes”;
- “21,064 relief camps set up by various State Governments/Union Territories where the migrant labourers have been shifted and are being provided with basic amenities like food, medicines, drinking water, etc.”;
- “6,66,291 persons provided shelters and 22,88,279 persons provided food”;
- “police and the other administrative authorities directed to adopt a humane approach in dealing with migrant workers and stranded tourists”

7th April, 2020: Jagdeep Chhokar v. Union of India¹¹⁵

This was another PIL filed by Dr. Jagdeep Chhokar, a former director in Charge of the IIM-Ahmadabad, and Gaurav Jain, where it was contended that several Fundamental Rights of the migrant workers due to the lockdown were suspended u/A 19(1)(d) and 19(1)(e) and the State cannot do that. Also, they contended in their petition that Article 21 was heavily infringed by the State for the migrant workers as they were left with no food, no job and they were compelled to return to their homeland by foot – this also violated their right to live with human dignity. They also contended in their petition that since lockdown hurt the migrant workers disproportionately, it also infringed Article 14.

But the PIL produced no result as the bench of N.V. Ramanna, Sanjay Kishan Kaul and B.R. Gavai, JJ ordered them to seek reliefs from the respective high courts.

¹¹⁴ <https://www.scobserver.in/beyond-the-court/covid-coverage-migrant-labourers-31st-march-2020>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.casemine.com/judgement/in/5eba8cc59fca1929d2d567b8>

8th May, 2020: *Alakh Alok Srivastava v. Union of India*

16 migrant labourers were run over by a goods train on 8th May in Aurangabad¹¹⁶. Citing this, Alakh Alok Srivastava made an interim application in the court highlighting this. The application sought the court to direct all the District Magistrates across India to track the stranded migrant workers in many parts of the country and after considering the situation, to give them some humanitarian assistance. The bench of L. Nageswara Rao, S K Kaul and B R Gavai, JJ refused to pass any direction or interfere in the matter and remarked that what can be done if the migrant workers choose to walk.

25th May 2020: *Suo Motu Cognizance by the Supreme Court*

On 25th May 2020 some senior and renowned advocates like P Chidambaram, Indira Jaising, Prashant Bhushan, Gayatri Singh, Mihir Desai and others wrote a letter to the Supreme Court collectively¹¹⁷. The letter asserted that the SC's non-interference in the matter of the migrant workers continue to violate their Fundamental Rights. They also stressed that the issue of the migrant labourers are not merely some policy decisions that the court cannot interfere into such. The letter chiefly addressed the issues like free transportation, food, shelter to the migrant workers.

28th May 2020

Upon hearing the counsels of all the parties in the matter, *In Re: Problems and Miseries of Migrant Labourers*, the three-judge bench of Ashok Bhushan, R. Subhas Reddy and MR Shah, JJ gave the following directions to all the states and UTs¹¹⁸:

1. "The migrant labourers must not be charged with train or bus fares for travel. The States Governments must share the costs".
2. "The States and Union Territories Governments to provide free food and water to the migrant labourers".
3. "The State where travel originates must provide food and water during the travel".
4. "The State must ease the procedure for registration and establish a help desk for registration".
5. "Post-registration, the migrant labourers must be provided travel at the earliest".

¹¹⁶ <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/16-migrant-workers-run-over-by-goods-train-near-aurangabad-in-maharashtra/article31531352.ece>

¹¹⁷ <https://thewire.in/law/supreme-court-migrant-workers-lawyers-letter>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.scobserver.in/beyond-the-court/covid-coverage-migrant-labourers-28th-may-2020>

6. *“The migrant labourers who are walking their way back home must be provided travel and food”.*
7. *“Once the migrant labourers reach their home states, they must be given free health screening and other facilities”.*

31st July: Registration of Migrant labourers by the states

On this date, the SC passed a comprehensive order based upon three Acts, namely, *Interstate Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979*, *Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996* and *Unorganized Workers’ Social Security Act, 2008*, and passed the states and the UTs to register the migrant workers to better facilitate them for availing relief measures.

13th May 2021: Atmanirbhar Scheme, Community Kitchens and Transportation

After a long time from 9th September 2020, SC sat on the matter of the migrant workers’ crisis and passed the following interim directions¹¹⁹:

- *“Provision of dry rations under the Atma Nirbhar Scheme or any other scheme, by the Central Governments and the State governments. Specific directions were provided to not ask for identity cards from the migrant workers”.*
- *“The states of Uttar Pradesh, Haryana and NCT of Delhi were directed to ensure adequate transport to stranded migrant labourers”.*
- *“These three states were also directed to open community kitchens in “well-advertised” places in the National Capital Region”.*

24th May 2021: Central Database for the implementation of the Schemes¹²⁰

After the order dated 13th May, it was seen that the *Atmanirbhar Scheme* was not started and the situation was graver than the previous year. Although transportation was not a big issue this year, providing cooked food to the stranded migrant workers was a greater challenge. Within one year of the nationwide lockdown, 24 crore people were pushed below the poverty line and hence providing cooked food under the *Atmanirbhar Scheme* or any other scheme was of utmost importance.

In its order, the SC stated that all the stranded migrant workers must be provided with cooked food under any available scheme. Also, it stated that the community kitchens must be set up and started to provide two meals per day.

¹¹⁹ <https://www.scobserver.in/beyond-the-court/covid-coverage-migrant-labourers-13th-may-2021>

¹²⁰ <https://www.scobserver.in/beyond-the-court/covid-coverage-migrant-labourers-24th-may-2021>

CHAPTER – 10

Conclusion

From the study taken up by the current researcher and the facts examined and evaluated, it is his considered opinion that the laws which are presently at our disposal are not enough to alleviate the miserable conditions of the migrant workers in our country.

That the existing laws are not sufficient to enable the migrant workers to live a life with human dignity, which is their Fundamental Right and a Human Right, is not to be solely blamed upon the enforcement wing, i.e., the justice system of this country. There are inherent flaws in the statutes themselves that are responsible for the present situation of migrant workers.

Not only that, the stance taken by the Indian State in this matter is too objectionable to be overcome by any structural enhancement of the legal system. Various Government wings, from the very outset of this pandemic, were reluctant to identify it as a serious threat and never employed entry-level precautionary measures to contain the infection. Instead, it took measures using an archaic statute and considered the people of this country as subjects to be ruled. The whole world had never seen a pandemic like this in the last one hundred years, and so the leaders of nations were in confusion about their plan and policy decisions regarding combating the pandemic. That said, the plans and actions taken solely depend on the scientific outlook of a state towards a pandemic. And India from the very beginning lost this battle in this area. It never followed the history and scientific discovery of modern medical science since the last five decades and went on on its own to allow various situations that became fatal for its general population. In doing so, it did not have any statutes regarding combating a pandemic of this kind, and it relied heavily upon criminal major Acts like IPC and CrPC and the police administration.

While this being the scenario, the migrant workers were left out in the entire planning of the Indian State. The resulting plight of the migrant workers who live in abject poverty has opened up already-existing bruises in the Indian democratic system which the rulers boast as the *biggest democracy* in the world.

That democracy is withering away, making way for another India where the majority of the working population are left out, and the *dance of democracy* is only perceived from the heights of *Antilia*¹²¹.

¹²¹ Mukesh Ambani's palace in Mumbai, the second most expensive house in the world after the Buckingham Palace.